

CANINE BRUCELLOSIS DUE TO *B. CANIS*

Canine brucellosis appears to be expanding in Western Europe in breeding, but also in private dogs, even in castrated animals in shelters. The veterinarian and lab staff must know how to identify, detect and manage this zoonosis. Human infections are rarely reported, but probably underestimated because of the possibility of asymptomatic cases and the lack of a validated indirect diagnostic technique. The first observations of human infection with *B. canis* isolated from blood cultures date from the 1970s. In almost all cases, contact with a domestic dog is identified, and in some cases, contact with a dog infected with *B. canis* is well documented, especially during abortion. Children can get infected as well. The clinical manifestations and severity of *B. canis* infections do not appear to differ from those observed during infections with other *Brucella* species. When symptomatic, the infection may take different clinical forms, including several nonspecific symptoms such as intermittent fever, chills, loss of appetite, weight loss, headache, backache, or joint pain...

This infection is endemic in dogs in many parts of the world, with a predominance in Central and South America, southern United States and Asia. Recently, an increasing number of cases were described in Eastern and Western Europe. Over the past two decades, studies published in these endemic areas have reported moderate to high seroprevalence, ranging from about 6% to 35% (Hensel et al., 2018).

Canine brucellosis is mainly caused by *Brucella canis*. This *Brucella* species was discovered in 1966 - 1967 in the USA during a study of abortion in one beagle kennel, the organism was isolated from aborted tissue and vaginal discharge.

One major specificity of this species is related to its antigenic properties, because its membrane contains a surface polysaccharide called "rough" which explains that serological tests conventionally used in ruminants or suids do not work to detect antibodies against *B. canis*. Canids (domestic and wild) are the natural reservoirs of *B. canis*.

It should be noted that in areas where animal brucellosis is endemic, canine infections with *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus*, and *B. suis* (with the potential for transmission to humans) may occur, when dogs come in contact with infected livestock (spill-over), or consume products from infected animals. This may concern hunting or shepherd dogs for example.

Canine brucellosis is an important cause of reproductive failure in dogs and can also cause severe complications, such as discospondylitis, lameness, neck or back pain. In the bitch, the easiest sign to recognize is a late miscarriage that occurs between day 45 of gestation and term. However, miscarriage may occur earlier and go unnoticed: the bitch is apparently infertile. Smaller litters (embryonic resorption) or stillborn puppies are also observed. Some puppies survive, remain infected and therefore potential contaminants. In males, *B. canis* infection frequently causes chronic epididymitis, which is almost asymptomatic, which can lead to an alteration of the spermogram within a few weeks. More rarely, orchitis and/or prostatitis can be observed. However, the clinical signs of *B. canis* infection in dogs are not pathognomonic, and infection can be subclinical.

This disease can be transmitted during mating, but it seems that the oronasal routes of contamination and, to a lesser extent, conjunctival, are predominant. In addition, aerosol transmission, and therefore by the respiratory route, seems possible and would partly explain the fast spread in kennels. Sexual transmission (mating, licking after miscarriage) is also a cause of contamination. Vulvar discharges may remain contaminated for several weeks. Excretion in semen and urine is frequently observed within 4-8 weeks of infection, after which it may remain intermittent for several months or even years. In humans, contamination is possible if persons are in close contact with dogs (repeated contact, cleaning, whelping, surgery on infected animals, contact with genital secretions, urine and faeces of infected dogs) or by laboratory exposure.

Indirect contamination, via social areas, housing and shared equipment (water or feeding bowls, veterinary equipment) must be considered in places where dogs are in larger numbers (breeding, gatherings, shelters...). The environmental survival of *Brucella* is favoured in humid conditions and low temperatures ($\leq 4^{\circ}\text{C}$). When conditions are optimal, *Brucella* can survive for more than two months in water at 20°C , two to four months in soil and on fresh grass in a moist environment and/or in the presence of organic waste.

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The serological screening and direct identification of the bacterium are required to confirm the diagnosis. In case of canine brucellosis, diagnosis from blood is complicated both with indirect and direct methods, due to limited intrinsic performances of serological tests and intermittent bacteraemia. Variable sensitivity and specificity of current serological tests decreases the diagnostic accuracy.

Prevention is based on general hygiene measures (wearing gloves, hand hygiene, cleaning litter boxes) and even wearing a surgical mask in high-risk situations. It is recommended to implement biosecurity measures in kennels. For example, small groups of dogs should be kept separated, when new dogs are introduced; six-week quarantine with serological testing at the beginning and the end of quarantine; testing of animals before importation; testing of males used for breeding.

The therapy is difficult and not definitive. Sterilization accompanied by prolonged antibiotic treatment does not guarantee healing. The infected animal has to be isolated so that it does not contaminate other dogs and will have to be followed for life (risk of relapse). Antibiotic treatment can be accompanied by undesirable effects (liver and kidney toxicity).

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